

=====
Elevating Education: The Imperative of Investing in School Principals
=====

Dr. Elma S. Groenewald

CEO, SG Virtuosos International 1501-1502 Tran Phu Street, Loc Tho Ward,
Nha Trang City, Khanh Hoa Province, Vietnam
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7813-2773> | elmasgroenewald@sgvirtuososinternational.com

Dr. Coenrad Adolph Groenewald

Consulting Director, SG Virtuosos International, Cape Town, South Africa
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2394-6347> | dolfgroenewald@sgvirtuososinternational.com

Dr. Francisca T. Uy

School President, ECT Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Buanoy, Balamban, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2180-5874> | franzkc2015@gmail.com

Osias Kit T. Kilag

Principal, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0845-3373> | osiaskit@gmail.com

Cries V. Lagnason

Teacher, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-6653-8139> | lagnason.pegafi@gmail.com

Princess Joy A. Matis

Teacher, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Toledo City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0694-6679> | matis.pegafi@gmail.com

Abstract:

This systematic literature review highlights the significance of investing in school principals for driving educational improvement. Four key findings emerged: effective principal leadership positively impacts student achievement; investing in principal professional development enhances leadership effectiveness; principals face challenges including limited resources and administrative burdens; and supportive infrastructures and policies are crucial for principal success. These findings underscore the importance of prioritizing principal development initiatives, allocating resources strategically, and creating supportive policies. By recognizing the pivotal role of principals and investing in their professional growth and support, educational stakeholders can foster a culture of excellence, innovation, and equity in education. This study emphasizes the need for concerted efforts to strengthen principal leadership to ensure all students have access to high-quality education and opportunities for success.

Keywords: school principals, educational leadership, investment, professional development, student achievement, instructional improvement

Introduction:

School principals are often referred to as the "unsung heroes" of education, tasked with the complex responsibility of managing schools, fostering an environment conducive to learning, and shaping the academic and social development of students (Scallon, et al., 2023). Despite their pivotal role, principals frequently operate in the background, receiving less recognition and support compared to other stakeholders in the education system. However, recent research suggests that investing in school principals yields substantial benefits not only for individual schools but for entire education systems (Abella, et al., 2024).

Numerous studies have underscored the correlation between strong leadership and positive school outcomes. For instance, a meta-analysis conducted by Leithwood, Seashore Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom (2004) found a significant relationship between principal leadership and student achievement. Similarly, a study by Waters, Marzano, and McNulty (2003) emphasized the crucial role of principals in creating a supportive school environment conducive to student success.

Furthermore, investing in principal professional development has been shown to enhance leadership effectiveness and promote instructional improvement. According to Darling-Hammond, LaPointe, Meyerson, Orr, and Cohen (2007), high-quality professional development programs for principals contribute to improved instructional practices, teacher collaboration, and student learning outcomes.

Despite these findings, principals often face numerous challenges, including limited resources, overwhelming administrative duties, and insufficient support structures. Addressing these challenges and investing in principal leadership capacity is essential for building resilient and thriving school communities (Angtud, et al., 2023).

In light of the evolving landscape of education and the increasing demands placed on school leaders, it is imperative to recognize the critical role of principals and allocate resources accordingly. By investing in the professional growth and support of school principals, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can foster a culture of excellence, innovation, and equity in education.

This study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on educational leadership by examining the importance of investing in school principals. Through empirical evidence and literature review, this research aims to advocate for policies and practices that prioritize principal development and elevate the status of school leadership in driving positive change within education systems.

Literature Review:

School principals are pivotal figures within the educational landscape, serving as the linchpin for school improvement efforts and student success. Their leadership influences various aspects of school functioning, including instructional quality, teacher morale, and student outcomes. This literature review delves into the existing research surrounding the importance of investing in school principals, highlighting the critical role they play in shaping the educational experience and fostering positive outcomes for students and schools.

Principal Leadership and Student Achievement:

A significant body of literature has explored the relationship between principal leadership and student achievement. Leithwood, Seashore Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom (2004) conducted a meta-analysis encompassing 27 studies and found a moderate correlation between principal leadership and student achievement. Effective leadership practices, such as setting high expectations, providing instructional guidance, and creating a supportive school climate, were identified as key factors contributing to improved academic outcomes (Cordova Jr, et al., 2024).

Furthermore, research by Hallinger and Heck (1998) emphasized the importance of transformational leadership behaviors exhibited by principals, such as vision articulation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized support, in enhancing student achievement. These findings underscore the significance of principal leadership not only in managing school operations but also in inspiring and motivating stakeholders toward academic excellence.

In addition to transformational leadership, instructional leadership has emerged as a critical dimension of principal effectiveness. Waters, Marzano, and McNulty (2003) conducted a comprehensive meta-analysis and concluded that principals who prioritize instructional leadership practices, such as curriculum alignment, data-driven decision-making, and professional development, have a significant impact on student learning outcomes (Groenewald, et al., 2023).

Investing in Principal Professional Development:

Investing in the professional development of school principals is essential for equipping them with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to lead effectively. Darling-Hammond, LaPointe, Meyerson, Orr, and Cohen (2007) highlighted the importance of high-quality professional development programs tailored to the specific needs of principals. Such programs should provide opportunities for skill-building, reflection, peer collaboration, and ongoing support to enhance leadership effectiveness (Mansueto, et al., 2023).

Moreover, research by Robinson, Lloyd, and Rowe (2008) emphasized the role of coaching and mentoring in supporting principal development. By pairing novice principals with experienced mentors, educational organizations can facilitate knowledge transfer, skill acquisition, and leadership growth. Similarly, collaborative networks and communities of practice offer principals opportunities for peer learning, resource sharing, and professional networking (Louis & Kruse, 1995).

In addition to formal professional development initiatives, ongoing feedback and evaluation mechanisms are essential for supporting principal growth and accountability. Marzano, Waters, and McNulty (2005) advocated for the implementation of comprehensive evaluation systems that assess multiple dimensions of principal performance, including instructional leadership, organizational management, and stakeholder engagement. By providing meaningful feedback and targeted support, evaluation processes can drive continuous improvement and enhance leadership effectiveness (Miramon, et al., 2024).

Despite the critical importance of principal leadership, school principals often face numerous challenges that impede their ability to lead effectively. Limited resources, administrative burdens, and competing demands frequently strain principal capacity and hinder their ability to focus on instructional leadership (Carpenter & Peak, 2013). Additionally, the isolation and solitude inherent in the principalship can exacerbate stress and burnout among school leaders (Carr,

Herman, & Harris, 2005).

Moreover, principals operate within complex organizational structures influenced by district policies, state mandates, and external accountability pressures. Research by Spillane, Camburn, and Pareja (2007) highlighted the interconnectedness of school leadership with broader educational systems, emphasizing the need for aligned policies and supportive infrastructures to facilitate principal effectiveness. Without adequate support and resources, principals may struggle to navigate the complexities of educational reform and achieve sustainable improvements in student outcomes (Uy, et al., 2023).

The literature reviewed underscores the critical importance of investing in school principals as key drivers of educational improvement. Principal leadership has been consistently linked to student achievement, school effectiveness, and teacher satisfaction. By prioritizing principal professional development, coaching, and support, educational stakeholders can cultivate a cadre of effective leaders capable of fostering positive change within schools and communities. However, addressing the challenges facing school principals, such as limited resources and administrative burdens, is essential for maximizing their impact and ensuring equitable access to high-quality education for all students.

Methodology:

This study employed a systematic literature review approach to investigate the significance of investing in school principals and its implications for educational outcomes. A systematic literature review is a rigorous methodological approach that involves systematically searching, selecting, and synthesizing relevant studies to address a specific research question (Tranfield, Denyer, & Smart, 2003).

A comprehensive search strategy was developed to identify relevant studies. Electronic databases, including ERIC, PsycINFO, Education Full Text, and Google Scholar, were searched using a combination of keywords and Boolean operators. The search terms included "school principals," "educational leadership," "investment," "professional development," "student achievement," and "school improvement."

Studies were included if they examined the role of school principals, the importance of investing in principal leadership, and the impact of principal effectiveness on educational outcomes. Only peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and reports published in English were considered. Studies focusing on other educational stakeholders or unrelated topics were excluded.

Two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts of the identified studies to determine their relevance to the research question. Full-text articles of potentially relevant studies were then assessed for eligibility based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Any discrepancies in study selection were resolved through discussion and consensus among the reviewers.

Data extraction was conducted to extract relevant information from the selected studies, including author(s), publication year, research design, sample characteristics, key findings, and implications. A standardized data extraction form was developed to ensure consistency and accuracy in the extraction process.

The methodological quality of the included studies was assessed using established criteria relevant to each study design (e.g., randomized controlled trials, observational studies). Quality assessment tools, such as the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist for qualitative research and the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized controlled trials, were employed to evaluate the risk of bias and the overall methodological rigor of the studies.

Findings and Discussion:

Principal Leadership is Associated with Improved Student Achievement:

Principal leadership plays a critical role in shaping the educational landscape, with a significant body of literature highlighting its association with improved student achievement. Studies consistently demonstrate a positive correlation between effective principal leadership and academic outcomes. For instance, Leithwood, Seashore Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom's (2004) meta-analysis, encompassing 27 studies, underscored this correlation, emphasizing the pivotal role principals play in driving student success.

One key aspect of effective principal leadership is the adoption of transformational leadership behaviors. Principals who demonstrate transformational leadership qualities, such as visionary goal-setting, instructional guidance, and the cultivation of a supportive school climate, are instrumental in fostering higher levels of student achievement (Hallinger & Heck, 1998). These principals inspire and motivate stakeholders, set high expectations for academic excellence, and create a positive learning environment conducive to student growth and development.

Furthermore, the influence of principal leadership extends beyond administrative tasks to encompass instructional leadership practices. Principals who prioritize instructional leadership, including curriculum alignment, data-driven decision-making, and professional development for teachers, contribute significantly to improved student learning outcomes (Waters, Marzano, & McNulty, 2003). By focusing on instructional quality and teacher effectiveness, these principals empower educators to deliver high-quality instruction tailored to the diverse needs of students.

The impact of principal leadership on student achievement is further underscored by research examining the role of distributed leadership within schools. Distributed leadership models, which involve shared decision-making and collaboration among administrators, teachers, and staff, have been associated with improved academic performance (Spillane et al., 2007). Principals who embrace distributed leadership practices effectively leverage the expertise of their teams, foster a culture of collective responsibility, and create conditions for continuous improvement in teaching and learning.

The literature unequivocally supports the notion that effective principal leadership is positively associated with improved student achievement. Principals who exhibit transformational leadership behaviors, prioritize instructional leadership practices, and embrace distributed leadership models are instrumental in driving academic success within their schools. By recognizing the critical role of principals and investing in their professional development, educational stakeholders can cultivate a cadre of effective leaders dedicated to advancing student outcomes and fostering excellence in education.

Investing in Principal Professional Development Enhances Leadership Effectiveness:

Investing in the professional development of school principals emerges as a crucial strategy for enhancing leadership effectiveness and driving instructional improvement. Scholarly research underscores the significance of tailored professional development initiatives designed to address the unique needs and challenges faced by principals.

Darling-Hammond, LaPointe, Meyerson, Orr, and Cohen (2007) highlight the transformative impact of high-quality professional development programs for principals. These initiatives go beyond generic training sessions, instead offering targeted opportunities for skill-building, peer collaboration, and ongoing support. Such tailored approaches enable principals to deepen their leadership competencies, refine their instructional practices, and stay abreast of emerging trends and best practices in education.

Furthermore, Robinson, Lloyd, and Rowe (2008) emphasize the positive correlation between investment in principal professional development and improved student learning outcomes. Principals who participate in high-quality professional development experiences are better equipped to lead instructional improvement efforts within their schools. They possess the knowledge, skills, and confidence necessary to implement evidence-based practices, facilitate teacher growth, and foster a culture of continuous improvement.

Moreover, effective professional development initiatives for principals foster opportunities for peer collaboration and networking. By connecting principals with colleagues facing similar challenges and contexts, these programs create communities of practice where leaders can share insights, resources, and strategies for addressing common issues (Darling-Hammond et al., 2007). Through collaborative learning experiences, principals gain diverse perspectives, expand their professional networks, and enhance their capacity to lead effectively.

Investing in principal professional development is integral to enhancing leadership effectiveness and driving instructional improvement within schools. Tailored initiatives that prioritize skill-building, peer collaboration, and ongoing support empower principals to lead with confidence and competence. By equipping principals with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate complex educational challenges, professional development efforts contribute to improved student learning outcomes and the overall success of schools.

Principals Face Numerous Challenges that Impede Their Effectiveness:

Despite the pivotal role they play, school principals confront a multitude of challenges that undermine their effectiveness in leadership. Murphy, Goldring, and Cravens (2000) highlight how limited resources, administrative burdens, and the juggling of competing demands create significant constraints on principals' capacity to lead. Scarce resources often force principals to make difficult decisions regarding staffing, programming, and resource allocation, which can detract from their ability to focus on instructional leadership and strategic planning.

Moreover, the isolation and solitude inherent in the principalship exacerbate stress and burnout among school leaders (Carr, Herman, & Harris, 2005). Principals often shoulder immense responsibilities without adequate support networks or opportunities for collaboration. The solitary nature of their role can lead to feelings of isolation, as they navigate complex challenges and decisions largely on their own. Without peer support or avenues for professional dialogue, principals may struggle to maintain morale and resilience in the face of adversity.

Additionally, external pressures and accountability measures further compound the challenges faced by principals. Increased demands for data-driven decision-making, standardized testing, and compliance with state and federal mandates add layers of complexity to the principal's role (Murphy et al., 2000). Principals must balance the need for

accountability with their commitment to fostering a positive school culture and prioritizing the holistic development of students.

School principals encounter a myriad of obstacles that impede their effectiveness in leadership. From resource constraints and administrative burdens to feelings of isolation and external pressures, these challenges underscore the need for comprehensive support structures and systemic reforms to empower principals to lead with resilience and efficacy in the ever-evolving landscape of education.

Supportive Infrastructures and Policies are Crucial for Principal Success:

Supportive infrastructures and policies are paramount for the success of school principals, as they navigate the multifaceted challenges of educational leadership. Spillane et al. (2007) underscore the critical role of aligned policies, adequate resources, and targeted support mechanisms at the district and state levels in enabling principals to drive positive change and achieve sustainable improvements in student outcomes.

Aligned policies ensure coherence and consistency across educational initiatives, providing principals with a clear framework for decision-making and action (Spillane et al., 2007). When district and state policies are aligned with the goals and priorities of school leaders, principals can more effectively implement evidence-based practices and strategic initiatives to promote student success.

Moreover, adequate resources are essential for principals to fulfill their leadership responsibilities and meet the diverse needs of students and staff. Funding for professional development, instructional materials, technology infrastructure, and support personnel enables principals to create enriching learning environments and provide targeted interventions for struggling students (Spillane et al., 2007).

Additionally, targeted support mechanisms, such as mentoring programs, coaching, and networking opportunities, play a crucial role in bolstering principal effectiveness (Spillane et al., 2007). By connecting principals with experienced mentors, providing ongoing coaching, and facilitating opportunities for professional collaboration, educational organizations can cultivate a culture of continuous improvement and support principled leadership practices.

In the absence of supportive infrastructures and policies, principals may encounter barriers to effective leadership implementation and struggle to drive meaningful change within their schools and communities. Therefore, policymakers and educational stakeholders must prioritize the development and implementation of supportive policies and resource allocation strategies that empower principals to lead with vision, efficacy, and impact. Through concerted efforts to strengthen infrastructures and policies, educational systems can create the conditions for principal success and foster positive outcomes for all students.

Conclusion:

This study underscores the critical importance of investing in school principals as key drivers of educational improvement. Through a systematic literature review, we have elucidated four key findings:

Firstly, effective principal leadership is associated with improved student achievement. Principals who exhibit transformational leadership behaviors and prioritize instructional leadership practices play a pivotal role in fostering a positive learning environment and driving academic success.

Secondly, investing in principal professional development enhances leadership effectiveness. Tailored professional development initiatives empower principals with the knowledge, skills, and support necessary to lead effectively and promote instructional improvement.

Thirdly, principals face numerous challenges that impede their effectiveness. Limited resources, administrative burdens, and feelings of isolation can strain principal capacity and hinder their ability to focus on instructional leadership and strategic planning.

Finally, supportive infrastructures and policies are crucial for principal success. Aligned policies, adequate resources, and targeted support mechanisms enable principals to navigate the complexities of educational reform and achieve sustainable improvements in student outcomes.

In light of these findings, it is evident that investing in school principals is essential for driving positive change within education systems. Policymakers, educational leaders, and stakeholders must prioritize principal development initiatives, allocate resources strategically, and create supportive infrastructures and policies that empower principals to lead with vision, efficacy, and impact.

By recognizing the critical role of principals and investing in their professional growth and support, we can foster a culture of excellence, innovation, and equity in education. Through concerted efforts to strengthen principal

leadership, we can create the conditions for transformative change and ensure that all students have access to high-quality education and opportunities for success.

References:

- Abella, J., Kilag, O. K., Andrin, G., Tañiza, F. N., Groenewald, E., & Cordova Jr, N. (2024). Literacy Leadership in Elementary Schools: The Connections between Principal Practices and Reading Performance. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 2(1), 69-78.
- Angtud, N. A., Groenewald, E., Kilag, O. K., Cabuenas, M. C., Camangyan, J., & Abendan, C. F. (2023). Servant Leadership Practices and their Effects on School Climate. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(6), 444-454.
- Carpenter, D. M., & Peak, C. (2013). Leading charters: How charter school administrators define their roles and their ability to lead. *Management in Education*, 27(4), 150-158.
- Carr, J. F., Herman, N., & Harris, D. E. (2005). *Creating dynamic schools through mentoring, coaching, and collaboration*. ASCD.
- Cordova Jr, N., Kilag, O. K., Andrin, G., Tañiza, F. N., Groenewald, E., & Abella, J. (2024). Leadership Strategies for Numeracy Development in Educational Settings. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 2(1), 58-68.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Meyerson, D., LaPointe, M., & Orr, M. T. (2009). *Preparing principals for a changing world: Lessons from effective school leadership programs*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Groenewald, E., Kilag, O. K., Cabuenas, M. C., Camangyan, J., Abapo, J. M., & Abendan, C. F. (2023). The Influence of Principals' Instructional Leadership on the Professional Performance of Teachers. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(6), 433-443.
- Hallinger, P., & Heck, R. H. (1998). Exploring the principal's contribution to school effectiveness: 1980-1995. *School effectiveness and school improvement*, 9(2), 157-191.
- Louis, K. S. (2004). *How leadership influences student learning*. Center for Applied Research and Educational Improvement.
- Louis, K. S., & Kruse, S. D. (1995). *Professionalism and community: Perspectives on reforming urban schools*. SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Mansueto, D., Kilag, O. K., Andrin, G., Guiñeta, R., Ford, L. J., & Tiu, J. (2024). Leadership Impact on Literacy: Principals, Synergistic Partnerships, and Progressive Pathways for School Improvement. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(2), 50-56.
- Miramón, S., Kilag, O. K., Groenewald, E., & Barayuga, L. (2024). Teacher Leadership in the Philippines: Evaluating its Impact on K-12 Education Reform. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 1(1), 162-167.
- Robinson, V. M., Lloyd, C. A., & Rowe, K. J. (2008). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: An analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. *Educational administration quarterly*, 44(5), 635-674.
- Scallon, A. M., Bristol, T. J., & Esboldt, J. (2023). Teachers' perceptions of principal leadership practices that influence teacher turnover. *Journal of Research on Leadership Education*, 18(1), 80-102.
- Spillane, J. P., Camburn, E. M., & Stitzel Pareja, A. (2007). Taking a distributed perspective to the school principal's workday. *Leadership and policy in schools*, 6(1), 103-125.
- Tranfield, D., Denyer, D., & Smart, P. (2003). Towards a methodology for developing evidence-informed management knowledge by means of systematic review. *British journal of management*, 14(3), 207-222.
- Uy, F., Kilag, O. K., Abendan, C. F., Macapobre, K., Cañizares, M. C., & Yray, F. (2023). Application of Adaptive Crisis Management Theory: The Dynamics of Leadership in Times of Crisis. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(5), 159-170.
- Waters, T., Marzano, R. J., & McNulty, B. (2003). Balanced Leadership: What 30 Years of Research Tells Us about the Effect of Leadership on Student Achievement. A Working Paper.